

A NOTE ON THE EFFECT OF SURFACE ACTIVE AGENTS ON ACID ALKALI INDICATORS

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In recent communications (Mehrotra, *Curr. Sci.*, 1947, 16, 345; *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1948, 2, 36), the applicability of Congo red as adsorption indicator in argentometric titrations has been described. Congo red (diphenyl bisazo- α -naphthylamine-4-sulphonic acid) has been recommended for use as acid alkali indicator and it shows a change of colour from blue-violet to red in the p_H range of 3 to 5. In the above communications, it has been described that if the p_H be maintained at 3 to 5, then in the titration of Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , CNS^- ions against silver ions, a sharp colour change from blue (or green in the case of bromide and iodide) to red occurs on the coagulated particles in the more concentrated solutions. If the titrating solutions be dilute or if the silver halide be kept in the suspension phase by the addition of a protective colloid like dextrin, then the above colour change occurs in the suspension phase. Similarly, in the reverse titrations of silver ions against halide ions, the opposite colour change, red to blue (or green), occurs, even if the p_H of the solution is maintained at a constant value of 4. The observation is similar to those of a number of previous workers (Smith and Jones, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1934, 38, 248; Hartley, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 30, 444; Hartley and Roe, *ibid.*, 1940, 36, 106; Krishnappa, Doss and Rao, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1946, 23A, 47), who have shown that the surface active agents like the wetting agents Ipegon T (sodium salt of oleyl-N-methylamine) and Nekal BX affect the p_H of the medium in which they are shaken. In the present communication, similar observations are recorded for purely inorganic surface active agents.

A sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer solution was prepared having a p_H 4. To 10 c.c. of this buffer solution were added 10 c.c. of say $N/25$ -potassium chloride solution and about 1 c.c. of 2 % dextrin solution and a drop of 0.2% Congo red solution. Silver nitrate solution of nearly the same strength as the chloride solution was run in. The suspension remained blue in shade so long as the chloride ions were present in excess. Just with the addition of half a drop of the silver nitrate solution in excess, the suspension changed its colour suddenly from blue to red. The above colour change is quite reversible; if to the red suspension is added a drop or two of the chloride solution, it again becomes blue. If we consider the change in the p_H of the solution, then the addition of a drop of silver nitrate or the chloride solution cannot be expected to produce any change in the p_H of the suspension. If the silver nitrate solution affects the p_H of the suspension at all, it can have the tendency to make the suspension, if unbuffered, a little more acidic owing to its hydrolysis, and hence any colour change due to p_H alone should turn the indicator more blue, rather than red. To obviate any possible source of the change in the acidity of the suspension, the observations were taken in a buffered solution. Hence, the above colour changes cannot be explained on the change of the acidity of the suspension.

The observations can, however, be easily explained if we take into account the part played by the surface of the silver halide molecules. The surface of the silver chloride is charged positively in the presence of excess of silver ions due to the adsorption of the silver ions (Lottermoser, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1905, *ii*, 72, 39, 1906, 73, 374), and this positively charged surface exerts a powerful attraction towards the red anions of the indicator, which are preferentially adsorbed. Hence, the equilibrium

is shifted towards the right and the suspension exhibits a colour change towards red. In the reverse case, the particles of silver halide being negatively charged in the presence of excess halide ions adsorb the blue cations of the indicator preferentially and the equilibrium shifts towards the left with the suspension changing blue in shade. Thus, though the p_H of the medium remains constant, the colour change of the acid alkali indicator is brought about by the change in the sign of the charge on the surface of the silver halide particles.

A similar observation has been made by Berg and Becker (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1940, 119, 81) with their newly discovered indicator Indoxine (5:8-quinoline-quinone-8-hydroxy-5-quinolyl-5 imide) which they have recommended both as acid alkali as well as adsorption indicator. In acid alkali titration, the dye changes its colour from red to blue in the p_H range of 6 to 8. They have shown that if a chloride solution is taken, maintained acidic by acetate buffer and a drop or two of the indicator added, then the addition of silver nitrate solution in excess turns the colour of the precipitate from red to blue and *vice versa*. The cause of the effect is similar to that described above.

Similar effects have been observed with $(\text{BaSO}_4)_\text{Ba}^{++}$ micelles which have been shown to adsorb Congo red with the development of red colour (Riegel and Ridson, *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 64, 304).

Thus, as the above observations show, the colorimetric determination of p_H of solutions is affected by not only the organic surface active agents like Ipegon-T and Nokal BX, but also by the inorganic surface active materials like the positively or negatively charged precipitates and suspensions and hence care should be taken that they should not be present while determining the p_H of a solution colorimetrically.

Further quantitative work on the apparent shift of p_H in the above cases is in progress.

In conclusion, the author wishes to thank Prof. N. R. Dhar for his interest and encouragement.